

FACTSHEET

Concise Labelling & Certification of Bio-based Products

Counteracting Greenwashing and Increasing Sustainable Purchasing Decisions!

Many consumers want to make sustainable purchasing choices but struggle in their effort to do so. Consumers feel overwhelmed and not competent for the decision which materials are eco-friendly and which are not.¹ Here, labelling and certification schemes (LCS) adapted for bio-based supply chains could provide a simple, official and trustworthy support system to distinguish eco-friendly from conventional products and enable consumers to make informed and sustainable purchasing decisions. In addition, certification and labelling play a crucial role for impeding greenwashing and instead providing credible and reliable sustainability information. LCS can also help facilitate the tracking and traceability of biological resources throughout value chains, fostering transparency and accountability among stakeholders of the bio-based industry.

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Definitions

Label and Certification Schemes (LCS)

LCS refer to frameworks or schemes established to assess and confirm the compliance of products, processes or services with specific standards or criteria.² The labels and certifications awarded under these schemes serve as visible indicators to consumers, businesses and stakeholders, confirming characteristics such as quality, safety, sustainability or compliance with industry standards. In contrast to mandatory LCS, that companies need to hold by law (e.g., EU energy efficiency labelling), voluntary LCS can be freely chosen by a company.

Certification Bodies

Organisations or agencies responsible for assessing and verifying compliance with standards and issuing certifications.³ Certification bodies typically conduct audits, inspections, or tests to evaluate whether a product, process, or service meets the specified requirements.

Labels for Bio-based Products

Labels specifically designed for products derived from renewable biological resources such as plants or organic residues. These labels indicate that a product is made (wholly or with a certain share) from biological resources and may also highlight sustainability information or inform about biodegradability of a product.⁴ Labels can either target businesses (B2B) or consumers (B2C).

Challenges that hamper the uptake of bio-based products by consumers

Green Scepticism

Consumers are often unsure or lack the knowledge whether materials and products are really bio-based, safe, credible and/or environmentally friendly.¹ Also, bio-based products (from waste) are often incorrectly associated with lower quality (at least stability when not made of wood¹).

Greenwashing

Two EU surveys in 2014 and 2020 revealed that approximately 53% of environmental claims on products were vague or false, with 40% lacking verifiable evidence.⁵ Such lack of evidence can confuse consumers and potentially constitutes greenwashing, which is an objectionable practise that can damage consumer trust.

Low Availability of Bio-based Products

Consumers might be prevented from buying sustainably if bio-based products are not available, which can be due to low availability of biological feedstocks, value-chain challenges or inadequate infrastructure for the delivery of products.

Willingness to Pay

The often higher price for sustainable products might reduce the consumers' willingness to pay for bio-based products.

Suitability of LCS for Bio-based Products

Existing LCS mostly use indicators and criteria that have been developed for traditional feedstocks (e.g. wood) and their applications. LCS development for novel bio-based products has been hampered by their limited market volume. Often, certifications do not sufficiently reflect the environmental and sustainability benefits.

Untransparent Sustainability Information

Sustainability claims and accompanying information need to be easily accessible to consumers. Here, careful product labelling could provide a remedy. However, various current logos lack clarity, have vague scopes and lack detailed information about the covered criteria.

Which LCS criteria are relevant to properly inform consumers about the sustainability of certified bio-based products?

Labels for bio-based products and green certificates can be a significant instrument to influence consumers' willingness to buy and pay for sustainable and eco-friendly products. This is because labels and certificates make it easier for consumers (especially those that are committed to sustainability) to understand the environmental impact of the products they purchase. Label information can serve as a trustworthy source of information. However, consumers should be offered ways to verify the green claim information.⁶ The 3-CO project identified seven key criteria for sustainability communication among LCS.⁷ These are:

Accessibility

Sustainability claims and accompanying information need to be easily accessible to consumers. This means that key criteria of LCS should be displayed on the website, should provide explanatory statements on the scheme, and that placement of claims alongside logos should follow concise and specified guidelines.

Clarity

Specific and easily understandable sustainability claims should follow various guidelines and regulations such as those by UNEP, ISO, and national authorities. Best practices include providing clear scope, precise information on sustainability aspects covered, utilising visuals effectively to enhance comprehension, ensuring clarity in grading systems, and combining descriptive and interpretative claims to build consumer trust and encourage action.

Relevance

It is necessary to evaluate that the selected criteria address pertinent issues, considering whether a green claim focuses on specific or broad sustainability concerns and whether it encourages meaningful behavioural change.

Transparency

In certification, public accessibility of documentation should become mandatory concerning operations, processes, governance, and criteria, with specific emphasis on disclosing the exact source of bio-based content and the nature of its environmental impacts reduction (as advocated by France's Ministry of the Economy and National Council on Consumption).

Reliability

The truthfulness of green claims should be guaranteed through robust data, methodology, and independent evaluation processes, with best practices including publicising supporting information and indicating third-party assessment on product packaging. This should enhance consumer confidence, as highlighted by various guidelines and authorities.

Sustainable Development

Considering environmental, social, and economic dimensions is crucial in sustainability communication to avoid burden-shifting and ensure inclusion of comprehensive criteria within LCS. It is imperative to educate consumers about the importance of sustainability issues and the impact of their purchasing decisions.

Display

The criteria described above should be reflected in the design of the label and the explanatory statements. Here, labels face the challenge of addressing all these issues while using limited space and overcoming language barriers.

The 3-CO Project

The 3-CO project aims to improve the sustainability performance and competitiveness of bio-based systems and will focus on consumer-oriented labelling options for sustainable industrial bio-based products. The supportive framework developed in 3-CO includes actionable guidelines for label design for LCS owners that reflect consumers' and other stakeholders' needs, digital solutions to support better-informed decision-making processes of consumers as well as policy recommendations on deploying social measures. By involving consumers and other stakeholders from the bio-based industries, 3-CO will make sure to identify and select relevant certification criteria and that information presented on the labels is not only verified but of value for consumers and the environment.

EU Laws and Directives

Recent advancements in environmental policy have underscored a pivotal shift towards sustainability and transparency in product manufacturing and consumption. Among these initiatives are the Green Claims Directive⁸, aimed at impeding misleading environmental claims, the introduction of digital product passports under the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation⁹, facilitating product traceability and lifecycle management, and the empowerment of consumers through the Green Transition Directive¹⁰, fostering informed decision-making in support of eco-friendly practices.

These directives signify a concerted effort to empower consumers, enhance product sustainability, and accelerate the transition towards a greener future. However, EU regulations often do not apply to value chains that originate from outside the EU.

References

- 1 <https://renewable-carbon.eu/publications/product/bio-based-products-green-premium-prices-and-consumer-perception-of-different-biomass-feedstocks/>
- 2 cf. definition of certification by <https://www.iso.org/certification.html>
- 3 cf. definition of certification body by <https://www.tuev-nord.de/en/company/certification/>
- 4 e.g. <https://www.dincertco.de/din-certco/en/main-navigation/products-and-services/certification-of-products/environmental-field/biobased-products/>
- 5 https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/circular-economy/green-claims_en
- 6 https://3co-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/02/d2.1_state-of-the-art-report-on-consumer-behaviour-towards-sustainable-products.pdf
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- 9 https://commission.europa.eu/energy-climate-change-environment/standards-tools-and-labels/products-labelling-rules-and-requirements/sustainable-products/ecodesign-sustainable-products-regulation_en
- 10 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/825/oj>

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